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**WORKSHOP PRACTICE SKILLS POSSESSED BY ELECTRICAL INSTALLATION AND
MAINTENANCE WORKS TRADE STUDENTS IN GOVERNMENT SCIENCE AND TECHNICAL
COLLEGES OF YOBE STATE, NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

This study sought to determine the workshop practice skills possessed by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade students in Government Science and Technical Colleges of Yobe State. The study was guided by two purposes, two research questions and two null hypotheses. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The area of the study was Yobe State of Nigeria. The population of the study was all the 3005 persons comprising 2955 SS II students and 50 teachers in EIMWT. The sample of this study was 341 respondents which comprises of 291 Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work Trade Students and 50 Teachers of Government Science and Technical Colleges of Yobe State. Purposive sampling technique was adopted to select nine schools out of seventeen Government Science and Technical Colleges of Yobe State. A structured questionnaire titled “Workshop practice skills possessed by electrical installation and maintenance works trade students” (WPSPEIMWTSQ) was used as the instrument for data collection. The instrument was trial-tested on 30 SS II Electrical installation and maintenance works trade students of GSTC Gamawa, Bauchi State. Data collected from the trial-test were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha and a reliability coefficient of 0.904 was obtained. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, t-test statistic was used in testing the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The data for the study were analyzed using SPSS version 25. Findings of research question one revealed that Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade students of Government Science and Technical Colleges in Yobe State possessed low workshop practice skills for using machine tools, as indicated by the overall grand mean below 2.50. Findings of research question two revealed that Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works students exhibited low workshop practice skills for using hand tools, with grand mean scores below the acceptable threshold. The study also revealed significant differences between teachers’ and students’ perceptions of the students’ and levels of competence, suggesting a gap between instructional expectations and actual student performance. It was recommended amongst others that Government Science and Technical Colleges in Yobe State should intensify workshop-based practical sessions to improve students’ proficiency in using both machine and hand tools.

Keywords: Workshop Practice, Skills Possessed, Machine Tools, Hand Tools

INTRODUCTION

Science and Technical Colleges are the types of secondary schools that focuses on providing students with both general academic education and practical technical and vocational skills. Science and Technical colleges are the primary vocational institutions in Nigeria and their purpose is to train students to acquire practical skills, knowledge, and attitudes

required by craftsmen and technicians at the sub-professional level (Osuyi, Osaigbovo, & Abusomwan, 2021). Science and Technical College is an educational institution that combines science-based learning (like Physics, Chemistry, Biology, Mathematics) with technical and vocational training (such as Electrical Installation, Welding, ICT, Automobile Technology, Woodwork, and Building Technology. Ochogba and Ordu (2019) described science and technical college as an institution that prepares individuals with technical skills relevant for employment and for admission into related courses in tertiary institutions. Recipients of this type of training are expected to possess vocational skills, knowledge, attitudes, a particular way of thinking and character qualities (Okolie et al., 2019). Similarly, Okwelle and Normakoh (2019) defined science and technical college as an institution that provides secondary level education in technical and vocational education and training. To achieve the aim of science and technical education, therefore, it requires that the individual students will pass through a formal training program in any of the technical institutions where technical and trade related programs in such courses as Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works, Welding and fabrication, building construction, Radio, Television and Electronic work, Motor Mechanic Works, and Carpentry and Joinery are offered (Eze & Okoye, 2020).

Furthermore, the practical aspects of the above listed technical trades can be effectively taught in the science and technical workshop. Workshop refers to a place where practical exercise take place. Workshop can refer to a room or building where manufacturing or repairs are carried out. This emphasizes the practical, hands-on aspect of the term. An electrical workshop is a designated space or facility equipped with tools, machines, instruments, and instructional materials where students or technicians are trained in the practical aspects of electrical installation, maintenance, and repair. It is an essential component of technical and vocational education, used to develop hands-on skills in areas such as wiring, circuitry, troubleshooting, and the safe use of electrical tools and devices.

Electrical workshops provide a simulated work environment that allows learners to apply theoretical knowledge in real-world scenarios, thereby enhancing competence, safety awareness, and job readiness in the electrical trade. Workshops encourage active participation and collaboration among participants, workshops are usually centered on a specific subject or project and they typically involve hands-on activities and skill development (Osuyi, Osaigbovo & Abusomwan 2021).

Practice refers to the application of knowledge or skills through repeated actions. In an educational or professional setting, it often emphasizes the practical aspect of learning which involves putting theoretical knowledge into practice. It is about doing, not just knowing. A core element of practice is repetition, which allows for the refinement of skills and the development of expertise, (Mahon et al., 2017). In essence, practice is more than just doing something; it is about the ongoing, contextualized, and often social process of applying and refining knowledge and skills. Skills contribute to economic growth both directly, through increased productivity, and indirectly, by creating a greater capacity in workers and firms to adopt new technologies and ways of working (International Labour Organization, 2023).

Skill is defined as desirable qualities required for certain forms of employment that do not depend on acquired knowledge: they include practical experience, common sense, the ability to deal with people, and a positive flexible attitude (Vasanthakumar, 2018). According to Lamri and Lubart (2023), Skill involves the integration of cognitive processes, practical abilities, and acquired experiences to achieve proficient performance. This definition highlights that skills are not innate but are developed through deliberate practice and training. In this study, skill is the ability of electrical installation and maintenance work trade students to establish good habit in the workshop by acting, thinking, and behaving well in order to prevent minor and major accidents that is involved in any operation or job that is related to electrical installation and maintenance work. Practice means doing something repeatedly in order to improve performance. For students to perform a

task with little or no record of accidents in electrical workshop, certain related skills are required by them. According to Okoye and Chukwuemeka (2021) skills are manual dexterities acquired through repetitive performance of an operation. There will always be a possibility of an accident or an injury when carrying out an operation in the science and technical workshops, therefore the provision of safety measure is as a priority.

A tool is piece of equipment or an item which is used with hand to make or repair something. This can be hand tool or tool. Hand tool is any tool or implement designed for manual operation. Also, it is a tool operated with hand without electricity or other source of power. Hand tool is a piece of equipment used for carrying out a task that uses human power and is not powered by any motor, engine, hydraulic, or pneumatic device (Schneider, 2025). Therefore, hand tools in this study refers to instruments or devices used to carry out electrical operations manually in the absence of machine tools. A machine tool is a critical component in the machining process, it is a power-driven device designed to shape or fabricates materials, typically metal, by cutting, boring, grinding, shearing, or other forms of deformation (Ronan, 2023). These tools range from simple hand tools like screw-cutting lathes to highly sophisticated CNC machines, which use computer numerical control for precision machining. Machines are therefore, mechanical or electrical devices for vocational technical operations. Operating simply means the activities carried out on a machine to do a work in the workshop.

The researchers will evaluate the workshop practice skills possessed by electrical installation and maintenance works trade students of government science and technical colleges of Yobe State of Nigeria. The study, if conducted, will provide data on the area of strength and weakness in students' practice skills in government science and technical colleges of Yobe state of Nigeria.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade (EIMWT) is a trade taught in technical and vocational education that requires a strong foundation in practical workshop skills. In Government Science and Technical Colleges (GSTCs) of Yobe State, students enrolled in EIMW programs are expected to acquire hands-on competencies in the use of electrical tools, wiring systems, maintenance procedures, and installation techniques, all of which are essential for their future employability and professional success. However, there is growing concern that many students graduate without mastering the essential workshop skills (Ogunmola, Agbo & Ifeacho, 2025). Reports from technical educators and stakeholders indicate that many EIMW students struggle with basic workshop procedures, lack proper tool-handling techniques, and often neglect safety guidelines during practical sessions (Omeje, 2019). Contributing factors may include insufficient instructional time, lack of modern equipment, inadequate supervision, poor safety culture. This will imply that a lot more Nigerians will remain unemployed and social vices like armed robbery and drug abuse will increase. Without confirming vital workshop skills that are lacking among the students, the above stated situation will remain worse and will be increasing. If this research is not carry out, it will be difficult to device effective ways of ensuring that the students do not graduate without acquiring most of the workshop skills that they need for employability and successful professional practice.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of the study was to determine the Workshop Practice Skills possessed by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade Students of Government Science and Technical Colleges of Yobe State, Specifically, the study seeks to determine:

1. Workshop practice skills for using machine tools possessed by electrical Installation and maintenance works trade student in government science and technical colleges of Yobe State.
2. Workshop practice skills for using hand tools possessed by electrical installation and maintenance works trade student in government science and technical colleges of Yobe State.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The study will be guided by the following Questions:

1. What are the workshop practice skills for using machine tools possessed by electrical installation and maintenance works trade students of government Science and technical colleges of Yobe State?
2. What are the workshop practice skills for using hand tools possessed by electrical installation and maintenance works trade students of government science and technical colleges of Yobe State?

HYPOTHESES

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level significance to guide the study:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean response of teachers and students on workshop practice skills for using Machine Tools possessed by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade students in Government Science and Technical Colleges of Yobe State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of teachers and students on workshop practice skills for using Machine Tools possessed by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade students in Government Science and Technical Colleges of Yobe State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Framework: David Kolb Experiential Learning Theory

The Kolb's experiential learning theory (1984) emphasizes that learning is a cyclical process rooted in experience, rather than just acquiring facts. Drawing on the work of Dewey, Lewin, and Piaget, Kolb proposed a four-stage learning cycle:

1. Concrete Experience (CE) – Learning by experiencing: hands-on or emotional engagement.
2. Reflective Observation (RO) – Learning by reflecting: observing and analyzing the experience.
3. Abstract Conceptualization (AC) – Learning by thinking: forming theories and models.
4. Active Experimentation (AE) – Learning by doing: applying new ideas to test their effectiveness.

Learners can enter the cycle at any stage but ideally move through all four stages for deep learning. The cycle is continuous—new experiences emerge from previous actions and learning. Kolb categorized learners based on how they perceive and process information into four styles:

1. Diverging (Feeling & Watching): Imaginative and good at viewing situations from multiple perspectives.
2. Assimilating (Watching & Thinking): Logical and theoretical, prefer abstract ideas over practical applications.
3. Converging (Doing & Thinking): Practical and solution-focused; like applying theories.
4. Accommodating (Doing & Feeling): Hands-on, intuitive, and adaptable learners who prefer action over theory.

These styles are flexible, not fixed, and can shift based on context or experience.

Applications of ELT

1. Curriculum & Instruction: Encourages a variety of methods like projects, reflections, lectures, and experiments to engage all stages and styles.
2. Professional Development: Especially useful in leadership and workplace training through experiential tasks.
3. Learner Self-Awareness: Helps individuals understand and adapt their learning strategies.
4. Team Collaboration: Understanding learning preferences can improve group learning and communication.
5. Assessment: Promotes diverse forms of evaluation beyond traditional exams.

Kolb’s ELT remains a foundational model in experiential education, encouraging active, reflective, and applied learning. Despite some criticisms, it offers practical insights for designing effective educational and professional experiences. Kolb’s Experiential Learning Theory is highly relevant to the development of workshop practice skills among Electrical Installation and Maintenance Work Trade (EIMWT) students. The theory emphasizes learning through experience, which aligns closely with how technical and vocational skills are best acquired—by doing, reflecting, conceptualizing, and experimenting.

Kolb’s Experiential Learning Theory provides a powerful framework for nurturing practical electrical skills among EIMWT students. Its cyclical learning model mirrors the hands-on, reflective, and applied nature of vocational training, making it particularly suited to the educational and occupational goals of Government Science and Technical Colleges Workshop in Yobe State.

METHODOLOGY

Design of the Study

The study uses descriptive survey research design.

Area of the Study

The area of the study is Yobe State, North-East, Nigeria;

Population of the Study

The population of the study was all the 3005 persons comprised of 2955 SS II students and 50 teachers in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade in the seventeen (17) Government Science and Technical Colleges in the seventeen 17 local government areas, and three educational zones of Yobe State.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample size of the study is 341 SS II students in in Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade of Government Science and Technical Colleges of Yobe State.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument for data collection is a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher and titled “Workshop Practice Skills Possessed by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade Students Questionnaire” (WPSPEIMWTSQ). The questionnaire items were rated on a four-point rating scale and the response options are as follows:

<u>Response Option</u>	<u>Abbreviatio</u>	<u>Numerical Value</u>
Very High	VH	4
High	H	3
Low	L	2
Very Low	VL	1

Reliability of the Instrument

To determine the internal consistency of the instrument, the instrument was trial tested on 30 SS II students from GSTC Gamawa, Bauchi State, which is outside the area of the study. Data collected from the trial test was analyzed using Cronbach Alpha and reliability coefficient.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected was analyzed using Mean and Standard Deviation to answer all the research questions, while the hypotheses were tested using t-test. All statistical analysis was done using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 27. A cut off point of 3.50 was taking as decision rule. Any item with a mean rating of 3.50 and above was considered as “Agreed”, while any item with mean below 3.50 was regarded as “Disagreed”. While testing the hypotheses were based on comparing the P-value obtained and the α -value at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that, if the P-value is greater than the α -value at 0.05 level of significance, the hypotheses was accepted but if the p-value was less than or equal to α -value at 0.05 level of significance; then, the hypotheses was rejected.

RESULTS

Research Question One: What are the Workshop Practice Skills for Using Machine Tools Possessed by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade Students of Government Science and Technical Colleges of Yobe State?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of the responses of teachers and students on Workshop Practice Skills for Using Machine Tools Possessed by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade Students

S/N	Items	Respondents n _T = 49, n _S = 262, n _G = 311						Remarks
		\bar{x}_S	σ_S	\bar{x}_T	σ_T	\bar{x}_G	σ_G	
1.	Ability in measuring and marking out work pieces before machining	2.26	0.87	2.31	0.58	2.26	0.83	Low
2.	Ability to set up a drilling machine for boring operations	1.86	0.75	2.33	0.77	1.93	0.77	Low
3.	Proficiency in using a grinding machine for sharpening tools	2.03	0.74	2.27	0.53	2.07	0.72	Low
4.	Ability to operate machine tools.	1.95	0.86	2.27	0.67	2.00	0.84	Low
5.	Ability to operate a lathe machine for simple turning operations	2.00	0.82	2.35	0.63	2.05	0.80	Low
6.	Ability to perform basic drilling operations on metal components.	1.77	0.80	1.92	0.67	1.80	0.78	Low
7.	Ability to use a bench grinder to sharpen tools.	2.09	0.68	2.18	0.75	2.10	0.69	Low
8.	Ability to cut and thread metallic conduit pipes.	1.84	0.79	2.08	0.70	1.88	0.78	Low
9.	Ability to use cutting fluids and lubricants appropriately during machining	2.33	0.91	2.33	0.83	2.33	0.89	Low
10.	Ability to align and clamp work pieces on machine tools	1.94	0.70	2.06	0.56	1.96	0.68	Low

\bar{x}_T = Mean responses of Teachers, \bar{x}_S = Mean responses of Students, σ_T = Standard Deviation of Teachers, σ_S = Standard Deviation of Students, \bar{x}_G = Grand mean, σ_G = Grand Standard Deviation.

The results presented in Table 1 reveal that both teachers and students rated the workshop practice skills for using machine tools possessed by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade students of Government Science and Technical Colleges in Yobe State as generally. The grand mean scores for all the listed items ranged between 1.80 and 2.33,

which fall below the acceptable proficiency benchmark of 2.50, indicating a weak level of competency. Specifically, students demonstrated low ability in measuring and marking out work pieces ($\bar{x} = 2.26, \sigma = 0.83$), setting up drilling machines for boring operations ($\bar{x} = 1.93, \sigma = 0.77$), and operating machine tools ($\bar{x} = 2.00, \sigma = 0.84$). Similarly, low proficiency was observed in performing basic drilling operations ($\bar{x} = 1.80, \sigma = 0.78$), cutting and threading metallic conduit pipes ($\bar{x} = 1.88, \sigma = 0.78$), and aligning work pieces on machine tools ($\bar{x} = 1.96, \sigma = 0.68$). The highest mean score ($\bar{x} = 2.33, \sigma = 0.89$) was recorded for the use of cutting fluids and lubricants during machining, though it still indicated low competence. Overall, the findings suggest that Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works students possess inadequate workshop practice skills for effective use of machine tools.

Research Question Two: What are the Workshop Practice Skills for Using Hand Tools Possessed by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade Students of Government Science and Technical Colleges of Yobe State?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of the responses of teachers and students on Workshop Practice Skills for Using Hand Tools Possessed by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade Students

S/N	Items	Respondents n _T = 49, n _S = 262, n _G = 311						Remarks
		\bar{x}_S	σ_S	\bar{x}_T	σ_T	\bar{x}_G	σ_G	
1.	Ability to correctly identify hand tools	2.10	0.72	2.27	0.60	2.12	0.71	Low
2.	Ability to applies the right tool for the right task	1.85	0.65	2.18	0.63	1.90	0.66	Low
3.	Ability to demonstrates proper handling technique.	2.09	0.57	2.29	0.61	2.12	0.58	Low
4.	Ability to follows safety rules while using hand tools	2.08	0.81	2.31	0.80	2.11	0.81	Low
5.	Ensuring hand tools are well-maintained after use.	2.27	0.81	2.37	0.70	2.28	0.79	Low
6.	Ability to use a screwdriver to install and remove electrical components	2.26	0.78	2.57	0.54	2.31	0.76	Low
7.	Ability to use pliers and cutters for bending and cutting wires	2.23	0.62	2.37	0.73	2.25	0.64	Low
8.	Ability to use wire strippers to prepare wires for connection	2.37	0.69	2.51	0.51	2.39	0.67	Low
9.	Ability to apply spanners or wrenches to tighten or loosen bolts and nuts correctly.	2.34	0.83	2.49	0.65	2.36	0.80	Low
10.	Ability to use hammer safely without causing damage or injury	2.37	0.75	2.57	0.50	2.41	0.72	Low

\bar{x}_T = Mean responses of Teachers, \bar{x}_S = Mean responses of Students, σ_T = Standard Deviation of Teachers, σ_S = Standard Deviation of Students, \bar{x}_G = Grand mean, σ_G = Grand Standard Deviation.

The results presented in Table 2 indicate that both teachers and students rated the workshop practice skills for using hand tools possessed by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade students of Government Science and Technical Colleges in Yobe State as low. The grand mean scores ranged from 1.90 to 2.41, all below the benchmark of 2.50, signifying low competence across the assessed items. Specifically, students showed limited ability to identify hand tools ($\bar{x} = 2.12, \sigma = 0.71$), apply the right tool for the right task ($\bar{x} = 1.90, \sigma = 0.66$), and follow safety rules while using hand tools ($\bar{x} = 2.11, \sigma = 0.81$). Similarly, low proficiency was observed in using screwdrivers to install or remove electrical components ($\bar{x} = 2.31, \sigma = 0.76$), using pliers and cutters for bending and cutting wires ($\bar{x} = 2.25, \sigma = 0.64$), and maintaining tools after use ($\bar{x} = 2.28,$

$\sigma = 0.79$). The highest mean score ($\bar{x} = 2.41, \sigma = 0.72$) was recorded for the ability to use a hammer safely, yet it still reflected a low skill level. Overall, the findings suggest that Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works students possess inadequate workshop practice skills for effectively using hand tools.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of teachers and students on workshop practice skills for using Machine Tools possessed by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade students in Government Science and Technical Colleges of Yobe State.

Table 3: t-test analysis of mean responses of teachers and students on space workshop practice skills for using Machine Tools possessed by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade students

	\bar{x}	σ	n	df	α	t_{cal}	P	Remark
Students	2.00	0.31	262	309	0.05	4.171	<0.001	Significant
Teachers	2.20	0.28	49					

KEY: \bar{x} = Mean, σ = Standard Deviation, n = Number of Respondents, df = Degree of Freedom, α = level of significance, t_{cal} = Calculated t-value, p = Significance (2-tailed)

The result presented in Table 3 shows the t-test analysis comparing the mean responses of teachers and students on workshop practice skills for using machine tools possessed by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade students in Government Science and Technical Colleges of Yobe State. The analysis revealed mean scores of 2.00 and 2.20 for students and teachers, respectively, with standard deviations of 0.31 and 0.28. At a 0.05 level of significance and 309 degrees of freedom, the calculated t-value ($t_{cal} = 4.171$) with a p-value less than 0.001 indicates a statistically significant difference between the two groups. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of teachers and students on workshop practice skills for using machine tools is rejected. This finding suggests that teachers and students differ significantly in their assessment of the students' level of competence in using machine tools.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of teachers and students on workshop practice skills for using Hand Tools possessed by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade students in Government Science and Technical Colleges of Yobe State.

Table 4: t-test analysis of mean responses of teachers and students on space workshop practice skills for using Hand Tools possessed by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works Trade students

	\bar{x}	σ	n	df	α	t_{cal}	P	Remark
Students	2.19	0.26	262	309	0.05	4.970	<0.001	Significant
Teachers	2.39	0.21	49					

KEY: \bar{x} = Mean, σ = Standard Deviation, n = Number of Respondents, df = Degree of Freedom, α = level of significance, t_{cal} = Calculated t-value, p = Significance (2-tailed)

The result presented in Table 4 shows the t-test analysis comparing the mean responses of teachers and students on workshop practice skills for using hand tools possessed by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade students in Government Science and Technical Colleges of Yobe State. The mean scores for students and teachers were 2.19 and 2.39, respectively, with corresponding standard deviations of 0.26 and 0.21. At 0.05 level of significance and 309 degrees of freedom, the calculated t-value ($t_{cal} = 4.970$) with a p-value less than 0.001 indicates a statistically significant difference between the responses of the two groups. Consequently, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference

between the mean responses of teachers and students on workshop practice skills for using hand tools is rejected. This implies that teachers and students differ significantly in their perception of the level of hand tool skills possessed by the students.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings of research question one revealed that Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade students of Government Science and Technical Colleges in Yobe State possessed low workshop practice skills for using machine tools, as indicated by the overall grand mean below 2.50. This suggests that students lack adequate proficiency in operating, setting up, and maintaining machine tools, an outcome that mirrors earlier findings by Okeke, Okafor, and Sunday (2024), who reported that mechanical craft teachers also demonstrated practical skill deficiencies in drilling and milling practices, underscoring the widespread nature of skill gaps in technical education. Similarly, Ibrahim, Tumba, and Isiyaku (2023) found that EIM students in Gombe State required significant improvement in practical skills to meet industrial expectations. Jonathan and Benson (2022) likewise observed that teachers themselves often lacked updated instructional competencies needed to transfer practical skills effectively, which negatively impacts students' performance. Furthermore, Onibode (2021) revealed that employers frequently express dissatisfaction with the technical competence of graduates from Nigerian technical colleges, citing insufficient mastery of machine tool operations. Okoye and Chukwuemeka (2021) added that integrating practical skills into technical education remains crucial for sustainable development, implying that weak skill performance among students hinders employability and productivity. Collectively, these findings affirm that inadequate training facilities, insufficient teacher competence, and limited industrial exposure continue to undermine students' mastery of machine tool operations in the technical colleges.

Findings of research question two revealed that Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works students exhibited low workshop practice skills for using hand tools, with grand mean scores below the acceptable threshold. This indicates poor competence in identifying, selecting, and handling tools effectively, aligning with Nnobulu, Alio, and Ugwuode (2024), who found that students in Enugu State displayed weak proficiency in practical hand tool manipulation due to inadequate workshop practice and outdated instructional methods. Amadi and Samuel (2022) similarly emphasized that many students in electrical/electronic trades lacked installation work skills necessary for sustainable livelihoods, primarily because of insufficient practice-oriented learning. Supporting this, Okeke et al. (2024) reported that a lack of in-service training for teachers contributes to students' inability to develop essential tool-use competencies. Ibrahim et al. (2023) also noted that improving hands-on exposure significantly enhances students' mastery of trade-specific tools and techniques. Furthermore, Oludolapo et al. (2021) found that even basic technology teachers in Lagos State possessed only moderate technical skills, limiting their capacity to demonstrate proper tool-handling procedures. Thus, the present finding reinforces the urgent need for improved workshop facilities, continuous teacher retraining, and competency-based learning strategies to enhance students' hand tool proficiency.

The finding from the testing of Hypothesis 1 revealed a statistically significant difference between the mean responses of teachers ($M = 2.20$, $SD = 0.28$) and students ($M = 2.00$, $SD = 0.31$) on workshop practice skills for using machine tools possessed by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works (EIMW) students in Government Science and Technical Colleges of Yobe State, $t(309) = 4.171$, $p < 0.001$. This implies that teachers perceived higher levels of machine tool handling skills among students than the students rated themselves. The significance of this result indicates a difference in perceived competence, which may arise from teachers' broader technical exposure and experience in workshop practices. This finding

is consistent with Okeke, Okafor, and Sunday (2024), who observed that mechanical craft teachers demonstrated superior mastery and evaluation of machine tool practices compared to students, primarily due to experiential knowledge gained through industrial training. Similarly, Ibrahim, Tumba, and Isiyaku (2023) reported that instructors in Gombe State technical colleges exhibited stronger technical competencies in machine tool operation and safety compared to their students. In agreement, Nnobulu, Alio, and Ugwuode (2024) emphasized that differences in skill perception between teachers and students often stem from limited practical exposure and insufficient workshop equipment. Jonathan and Benson (2022) further found that teachers generally evaluate students' technical proficiency more critically, identifying gaps in operational efficiency that students may overlook. Additionally, Amadi and Samuel (2022) noted that electrical/electronic trade students in Bayelsa State often lack the manipulative skills and safety consciousness required for effective use of tools, reinforcing the present finding.

The finding from the testing of Hypothesis 2 revealed a statistically significant difference between the mean responses of teachers ($M = 2.39$, $SD = 0.21$) and students ($M = 2.19$, $SD = 0.26$) on workshop practice skills for using hand tools possessed by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works (EIMW) students in Government Science and Technical Colleges of Yobe State, $t(309) = 4.970$, $p < 0.001$. This implies that teachers rated students' hand tool usage skills higher than the students' self-assessment, indicating variations in confidence levels and perceived competency. The significant difference suggests that while teachers recognize some level of skill attainment, students may still struggle with proper handling and application of hand tools during workshop activities. This finding agrees with Nnobulu, Alio, and Ugwuode (2024), who reported notable differences in teacher and student perceptions of practical skills in electrical installation, attributing such gaps to insufficient practice and lack of modern hand tools in technical colleges. Similarly, Ibrahim, Tumba, and Isiyaku (2023) found that students of EIMW trade in Gombe State exhibited inadequate proficiency in tool usage, which teachers attributed to limited industrial exposure. Okeke, Okafor, and Sunday (2024) also revealed that both mechanical and electrical students often require additional training in precision and control when using hand tools, reinforcing the present finding. In a related study, Amadi and Samuel (2022) highlighted that technical students lacked sufficient manipulative and installation work skills for sustainable livelihood, stressing the importance of regular practice. Furthermore, Jonathan and Benson (2022) reported that the mismatch between teachers' expectations and students' practical performance often reflects deficiencies in the instructional delivery of hand tool operations.

CONCLUSION

The main objective of this study was to determine the workshop practice skills possessed by Electrical Installation and Maintenance Works trade students in Government Science and Technical Colleges of Yobe State. From the findings, it can be inferred that the students demonstrated low levels of workshop practice skills in the use of both machine and hand tools. Furthermore, the study revealed significant differences between teachers' and students' perceptions of the students' and levels of competence, suggesting a gap between instructional expectations and actual student performance. These outcomes provide strong evidence that while students have there remains a critical need to strengthen their practical competencies for effective participation in technical and vocational tasks.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government Science and Technical Colleges in Yobe State should intensify workshop-based practical sessions to improve students' proficiency in using both machine and hand tools. Teachers should adopt demonstration, simulation,

and competency-based instructional methods that provide students with more hands-on experience and mastery of core technical operations.

2. Teachers and school administrators should increase supervision during workshop activities and collaborate with industries to provide students with real-world exposure through industrial visits, internships, and skill-development programmes that reinforce classroom learning with practical application.

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